

Islamic Education in Supply Chain System by Prioritizing Manners as a Success Factor of Millennial Generation on Socializing

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Abstract-The progress of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) in the Era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 requires that learning systems in schools must be developed by considering the supply chain. Since June 2006 the Tebuireng Islamic Boarding School has been developing an education system based on the supply chain strategy. In this development, the Tebuireng Islamic Boarding School begins with a religious-based education or theology that prioritizes manners in supply chain. In this case, we analyzed learning success factors based on Law Auguste Comte as the objective in this study. The study aimed to investigate the relationship between anticipation ability, supply chain, ability to accommodate and integration of education system with the mediation effect of self-organizing skills. In addition, a collaboration of 3 countries was also carried out to seek integration of schools in developed countries such as Japan and Turkey as a reinforcing factor for the success of the education system for the millennial generation in socializing. The results of the study provide very strong information and compatibility in the success of student learning, attitudes, and behavior as a millennial generation in the Industrial Revolution Era 4.0. The most dominant success factor in learning success based on the results of school integration in Japan, Turkey, and the TebuirengPesantren is the respect for others based on the formation of good characters, such as tolerance, respect, polite in speaking, and polite in acting. Besides, learning models such as Innovative learning are the most suitable models in the Industrial Revolution Era 4.0, because at this time almost all learning is based on the Internet of Things (IoT) as a very good learning media. **Kemajuan Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) pada Era Revolusi Industri 4.0.**

Keywords; *Islamic Educational System; Supply Chain, Millennial Generation; Japan; Turkey; Pesantren Tebuireng; Era of Industrial Revolution 4.0*

1. Introduction

Teachers in the Industrial Revolution Era 4.0 are teachers who have the task of providing quality education in a professional manner based on the Internet of Things (IOT) and supply chains in education and society. Wardiman Djojonegoro in this context once stated in his paper that our nation is preparing itself to have quality Human Resources Management (HRM). Characteristics of quality human resources are having the ability to master expertise in a field related to science and technology, able to work professionally with a quality orientation and excellence, and can produce superior works that are able to compete globally as a result of expertise[1]. As education personnel, professional teachers cannot be separated from the images given from other people[2].

In social life in this global era, teachers on the one hand are expected to be more moral than the general public but on the other hand new problems arise as challenges when teachers do not have the material capacity to have all access and information networks such as TV, books, magazines, Newspapers. The internet to improve their professionalism while at the same time enriching information about the development of knowledge and various dynamics of global life, so it is very difficult to imagine teachers appearing

more professional and having professional moral responsibilities as a consequence of this global era.

The standards of the current world are changed due to the grown rate of literacy, in the era of 4.0 industrial revolution, education has become the widely adapted mean for developing the character of students in the global world. The growth of technology, education and different other sectors has been viewed with the new world, therefore some sort of factors like supply chain that can help for the integration of proper education system can significantly elaborate the prevailing issues. Not only various educational programs has been founded significantly resulting in the developing world but has also gained much importance in characters and living standards. Islamic education is widely found in the character development with the means of sophisticated, meaningful and reputable capabilities within the students, while the context of supply chain has been found broader where the students caught to learn. Many schools have been developed, where the boarding schools of Islamic studies and Islamic states have been considered the most successful [3].

The government also seeks to overcome these problems in increasing teacher professionalism by holding teacher certification to improve their welfare. The attention of the government is expected to provide solutions to problems in the world of education, especially to teachers to remain committed to improving the quality of learning and the quality of education in the current global era. Facing such challenges, we need truly professional teachers. Competencies that must be possessed by a teacher in order to face the global era, i.e.:

Anticipation ability is the ability that must be possessed by an educator to anticipate and prevent problems both in the learning process and problems that may arise outside of learning. For example the ability to anticipate can be done by the teacher preparing infrastructure and everything so that there are no obstacles in the process of teaching and learning. An educator needs to approach his students to be able to recognize and identify problems faced by their students both related to academy and non-academy. Not only does it stop at recognizing the problem, but it also follows the selection of solutions to the problems faced by students and implements these solutions so that students' problems can be overcome. A teacher must be able to accommodate the differences found in students. The difference here can be in the form of needs between one individual and another individual. Teachers can accommodate the needs of students in relation to learning such as providing the need for knowledge, and infrastructure if able[4]. Attitude towards something. The teacher needs to determine what the references will be achieved As an

educator, the teacher must be able to reorient, namely reviewing an insight and determining and making students confident and motivated to achieve these goals[5].

Generic ability is a capability that must be possessed by an educator which includes cognitive strategies, and can also be known as the ability of the keys, core abilities (core skills), essential abilities, and basic abilities. Generic abilities include: communication skills, teamwork, problem solvers, initiatives and efforts (initiative and enterprise), planning and organizing, self-management, learning skills and technology skills[6].

Encourage yourself to want to regulate all elements of personal ability, control the willingness to achieve good things, and develop various aspects of personal life to be more perfect. How can a teacher become a professional and virtuous teacher if he cannot encourage, regulate, control, and develop all his personal resources? Therefore, the skill to manage oneself for a teacher is absolutely necessary in order to be able to carry out all their duties properly. Communication skills are the main skills that must be possessed to be able to foster healthy relationships anywhere, in the social environment, schools, businesses and offices, in the garden or anywhere. Most problems that arise in social life are communication problems. If communication skills are possessed, it will greatly help minimize the potential for conflict while opening opportunities for success. The ability that must be possessed by a teacher in order to be able to manage his students as well as his teacher's tasks in order to achieve the desired goals. Managing people by recognizing the emotions of others means that we have empathy for what other people feel. Mastery of these skills makes us more effective in communicating with others. This is what Stephen Covey calls empathic communication. Try to understand first before being understood. This skill is the basis for dealing with people effectively. In terms of assignments, the teacher functions to provide encouragement to students to be able to study harder, and give assignments to students according to the abilities and individual differences of the teaching participants[7].

2. Literature Review

The ability to mobilize development and change in that the teacher functions to do creative activities, find strategies, methods, ways, or new concepts in teaching so that learning is meaningful and gives birth to quality education. The teacher is responsible for directing the development of students as the younger generation who will be the heirs of the future and the teacher's role is to convey various advances in science and technology to the community.

The mastery of science and technology and the competitive spirit are also important things for professional teachers because they are expected to be able to bring or take their students through the world of science and technology to enter the global era of science and technology literacy, and very competitive.

In the global era the characteristics of teachers must be clearly and firmly maintained, among others:

- Having qualified science and technology
- Has a strong and good personality
- Have the skills to arouse students' interests in the field of science and technology

There are at least four preconditions for a teacher to be able to work professionally, i.e.:

- 1) The ability of the teacher to process / work around the curriculum,
- 2) The teacher's ability to link curriculum material to the environment.
- 3) The ability of teachers to motivate students to learn on their own.
- 4) The ability of teachers to integrate various subjects into a unified whole concept (the need for integrated learning).

Studying knowledge is a very noble work so that people who look for it must pay attention to noble ethics too. In this context a person who studies must have religious activities accompanied by polite social behavior (al-akhlāk al-karimah). Because morals is a behavior that originates from within human beings themselves. 1 The word morals comes from Arabic akhlaq which is the plural form of the word khuluq which means character, character, and habit. With the precedence of the word science which later became the science of morals ('knowledge al akhakhlaq) means what is meant is knowledge of character, manners, and human habits this means what is meant also by ethics[8].

In the book of AdābalAlimwaalMuta'allim, KH. Muhammad HasyimAsy'arireveal a lot about the ethics of students in studying, i.e.:

“Students to cleanse the heart of every persuasion, impurities, envy, jealousy, beliefs and bad views and despicable morals. This ethics is the main foundation for students to facilitate and obtain knowledge, namely cleanliness of the heart”.

Students must improve their intention to study, which is to aim at the essence of Allah SWT, practice it, turn on the Shari'ah, illuminate the heart, decorate the soul and draw closer to Allah SWT. Students must be enthusiastic, enthusiastic and really earnest in seeking knowledge when

they are young and in time while they are still alive. And not once persuaded by procrastinating (discipline / persevering).

Students to have the nature of qāna'ah (accept) in terms of food and clothing according to ability. Thus, students must avoid themselves from their spree-of-life attitude, wallowing in wealth, which will cause unhealthy competition, and give birth to hatred and envy between them. So, patiently will bring a student to be a noble person.

Boarding schools in the area of Islamic education has not provided positive aspects for the development of students but also have revealed the results that have seen in many studies. The achieved success factor is seen in many studies where the students are capable to deliver respect and tolerance after being studied in the Islamic schools, whereas the characters of supply chain have also been found very significant in the global and developed world. Various factors have been enumerated in studies about the manners prioritizing in the system of education, while the supply chain has also been contributed to such success factors which have been achieved while integration of such system. Some private institutions with lack of management and lack of prioritization have been caught with lack of character and system of education building in various countries, while in some counties the boarding system in context of Islamic education has widely supported the era of building the capable students.

Students in order to divide the time of day and night and take advantage of free time. Because the lost time is infinite in price. Students to reduce relationships because it reduces relationships. One of the important things that must be done by students, let alone associating with other types more if only to play and not concentrate in the lesson. KH. Muhammad HasyimAsy'aristated that students if they want friends, they should choose good friends, in terms of religion, beliefs, magic, cleanliness of the heart, tend to be kind, avoid evil, good self-esteem, and are not easy to argue with others.

The policy adopted by the Japanese government in the field of education is to eliminate discrimination / difference. In the Japanese government, anyone can enjoy education. People from all walks of life have the right to receive formal education. Japan also applies formal education levels such as in its country namely: 6-year elementary school, 3-year middle school and 3-year high school. This system is still applied by the Indonesian government to this day. One thing that weakens from the aspect of education is that the teaching system and curriculum are adjusted. Students have the obligation to attend basic military training and be able to memorize the Japanese national anthem. Similarly, the teachers, are required to use Japanese.

In addition, it can be said that the education system in Japan has similarities to the education system in our country where the level of education goes through 4 stages in general, 6-3-3-4 meaning that students must pass 6 years for the basic education stage, 3 years of junior high school, 3 years of senior high school, 4 years of tertiary education. That is because our country is a former Japanese colony so that part of the Japanese education system is still applied in our country with a few changes where our country is more focused on learning logic and final semester assessment as a determinant of student graduation while in Japan it is more focused on developing personality traits in relation to daily life and assessment are determined by the teacher / lecturer class by looking at student learning performance everyday as a determinant of graduation[9]. We need to know that the Japanese education system is built on principles:

We need to know that the Japanese education system is built on the principles of legalism: Education in Japan continues to uphold the rule of law and legalize the rights of every individual to obtain education without discriminating against anyone, ethnicity, religion, race, and among groups entitled to get proper education. Democratic Administration: The state provides the opportunity for anyone to obtain education at a cost that is still affordable by the people. The cost of Japanese education is sought to be affordable according to the financial community, providing scholarships for students who excel or are less able.

Neutrality: Japanese education is given to each student with their respective levels of education by prioritizing the view of the equality of each student without discriminating material background, family origins, gender, social status, economic position, ethnicity, religion, race, and between groups. Adjustment and determination of educational conditions: In the teaching process has a level of difficulty each adjusted for the levels of education being pursued. Decentralization: Dissemination of educational policies from the central government equally to all schools in the country so that the development and progress of the education system can be followed properly.

Education in Turkey has become one of the most important, if not the most important, single factors in determining one's social placement. This has been described as a hallmark of the elite, and has been found to be an important criterion that underlies the social differences between the Turks. Education, Daniel Lerner observed, distinguishes Turks to modern, traditional, and transitional, so that it performs important functions in the process of modernization. Education has been, and is still considered, an important condition for social mobility and work placement. Turkey's current school gap system follows a 5-3-3-6 year pattern. First level 5 years for elementary school. This basic

education starts from the age of 7 to 11 years or more. This stage is a compulsory learning stage.

The next level is 6 years for high school which is divided into two stages: 3 years at junior high school (Ortaokul), which accepts children aged 12-14 years, and 3 years at high stage (Lycee), for ages 15-17 years. Ortaokul is a public school in preparation for college. Most parents want their children to attend this public school, then after graduating specialized in vocational education. Lycee is also general and vocational, in addition to engineering. Some of these Lycees implement a co-education system, some specifically for men and some specifically for women.

In 2012, the government introduced the compulsory education system, known as 4 + 4 + 4. (4 years for basic education, 4 years of secondary education and after that, and the next 4 years), students are given the opportunity to choose a major in general education or religion[10].

The education system in Turkey in general can be said to be almost the same as the education system in Indonesia. The main Turkish national education system consists of two parts:

Formal education is a school system consisting of preschool educational institutions, basic education, secondary education and higher education, as well as education in Indonesia. In accordance with Basic Law No. 1739 for National Education. Basic Law of the Turkish National Education[11]. Non-formal education includes all activities held inside or outside the school. Pre-school education is optional education, aiming to make a mental, and emotional contribution to the physical development of children / students to help them obtain good habits (ahklak), which were emphasized while they were still in primary education. Pre-school education is provided in kindergartens, child care centers, nursery classes in primary schools and preparatory classes by various departments and related agencies, and the Turkish Ministry of National Education. Basic education, providing basic knowledge to children and ensuring physical, mental and moral development in accordance with national education goals. Generally it consists of education of children in the age group of 6-14 years. Eight years of basic education is compulsory for all Turkish citizens who have reached the age of six, there are also private schools but are still under state control. However, special foreign language lessons have been started since 4 years in basic education. Secondary education is classified into two categories of educational institutions, namely general and vocational high schools and technical high schools (lycées) where a minimum of three years of schooling is carried out after basic education.

The aim of secondary education is to give students an introduction to general culture at a minimum level and

prepare them to take responsibility for democratic societies, make them respect human rights and prepare them for higher education or business towards the interests of a prosperous life[9]. Private high schools, have foreign language preparation classes, are in line with the objectives of the education program, and in foreign language education integrated into science and mathematics groups. Islamic boarding schools are Islamic educational institutions that have been established for hundreds of years and still survive in Indonesia today. The existence of Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia is estimated to begin at the time of the entry of Islamic teachings in Indonesia brought by Islamic traders, trustees, preachers and so on to the archipelago. Since then, pesantren can be found in several different regions in Indonesia[12].

The positive value felt by the community towards the existence of pesantren has caused these Islamic educational institutions to be needed and remain standing today. Based on historical records, the pesantren gave birth to many scholars and figures who played an active role in participating in development in Indonesia and society in particular. Pesantren has characteristics that distinguish it from non-pesantren educational institutions in terms of concepts and products. The most basic characteristic of pesantren is simplicity with the aim of forming good human beings. In this study, observation or data collection was carried out directly (Figure 1)[13]. Data obtained from Forum Discussion Group (FGD) with teachers who are in school. Not only that, data using FGD was also conducted on students (local students and international students from various countries). The purpose of these two data retrieval is to mutually reinforce the results obtained from the FGD towards teachers and students (integrated). The method used in this FGD is to use a questionnaire survey made with 5 questions. In addition observations were made to obtain data related to the main learning methods, physical school, the phenomenon of student life related to the educational process. Interviews were also conducted to explore information that could not be covered through observation and connected with the laws of Auguste Comte.

Figure 1. Research Model in this study

The proposed hypotheses of this study are as under:

H1: These is positive association among anticipation ability and Integration of Education System.

H2: These is positive association among supply chain and Integration of Education System

H3: These is positive association among Ability to accommodate and Integration of Education System

H4: Self Organizing Skillshas positive mediation among the links of anticipation ability and Integration of Education System.

H5:Self Organizing Skills has positive mediation among the links of supply chain and Integration of Education System.

H6: Self Organizing Skills has positive mediation among the links of ability to accommodate and Integration of Education System

3. Research Methods

The questionnaire survey given in this study is random, and is anonymous as an objective form of data retrieval (Table 1). However, the provision of status information as (teacher or student) is written in this questionnaire with the aim to correlate the results of observations.

Table 1. Questions given in the questionnaire

	Score
Is the teaching and learning process done very well?	(1-5)
Is the teaching and learning process carried out always on time?	(1-5)
Does the knowledge provided to students meet all the learning curriculum needs?	(1-5)
Is the assignment in accordance with the material given?	(1-5)
Are the conditions of teaching and learning carried out interactively and efficiently?	(1-5)

Participants who helped in this study were drawn from 2 schools in Japan, 2 schools in Turkey, and 2 schools in Tebuiireng Islamic Boarding School, Jombang, Indonesia. The data for these 2 schools are taken from 1 Junior High School, and 1 High School in 2018. The data collection scheme can be seen in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Participants in this study

This study takes the questionnaire method to collect the data from the respondents and analyzed the data by using the Smart-PLS. The anticipation ability (AA) has 13 items, supply chain (SC) has 10 items, ability to accommodate (AAC) has 4 items, self-organizing skills (SOS) has 6 items and integration of education system (IES) has 4 items. These are shown in Figure 3 given below:

Figure 3: Theoretical Framework

4. Findings

The convergent validity show that items are strongly linked with each other and valid the convergent validity because Alpha and CR more than 0.70 and loadings and AVE are larger than 0.50 and these statistics are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Convergent Validity

Items	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
AA1	0.674	0.924	0.934	0.520
AA10	0.744			
AA11	0.699			
AA12	0.773			
AA13	0.766			
AA2	0.745			
AA3	0.669			
AA4	0.686			
AA5	0.690			
AA6	0.709			
AA7	0.730			
AA8	0.742			
AA9	0.737			
AAC1	0.655	0.646	0.811	0.590
AAC2	0.847			
AAC4	0.790			
IES1	0.740	0.798	0.868	0.623
IES2	0.753			
IES3	0.837			
IES4	0.823			
SC1	0.738	0.908	0.922	0.543
SC10	0.698			

SC2	0.690			
SC3	0.716			
SC4	0.749			
SC5	0.737			
SC6	0.711			
SC7	0.744			
SC8	0.771			
SC9	0.808			
SOS1	0.897	0.878	0.909	0.626
SOS2	0.848			
SOS3	0.724			
SOS4	0.671			
SOS5	0.748			
SOS6	0.836			

The discriminant validity show that constructs are not strongly linked with each other and valid the discriminant validity because Heterotrait Monotrait ratios are not larger than 0.90 and these statistics are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio

	AA	AAC	IES	SC	SOS
AA					
AAC	0.243				
IES	0.709	0.344			
SC	0.594	0.296	0.734		
SOS	0.549	0.406	0.762	0.706	

Figure 4: Measurement Model Assessment

The path analysis show that AA, AAC and supply chain have positive association with IES and accept the H1, H2 and H3 while SOS has positive mediation among the links of AA and IES, supply chain and IES and AAC and IES and

accept H4, H5 and H6. These statistics are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Path Analysis

	Beta	S.D.	t-values	p-values
AA -> IES	0.323	0.043	7.481	0.000
AAC -> IES	0.068	0.034	1.988	0.047
SC -> IES	0.271	0.052	5.234	0.000
AA -> SOS -> IES	0.058	0.016	3.594	0.000
AAC -> SOS -> IES	0.045	0.015	3.020	0.003
SC -> SOS -> IES	0.143	0.033	4.277	0.000

Figure 5: Structural Model Assessment

Observation results show that educational information in Japan has very good information in all aspects. All 5 aspects of using questions have very high average scores. This shows that, education in Japan has a system that has been developed based on the needs at this time. Moreover, Japan is a developed country and has been preparing for the next era, Era Society 5.0.

Table 5. Results of observation data (general) education in Japan, Turkey, and Indonesia

	Educational Aspects	Average value
Japan	Is the teaching and learning process done very well?	5
	Is the teaching and learning process carried out always on time?	5
	Does the knowledge provided to students meet all the learning curriculum needs?	5
	Is the assignment in	4.5

	accordance with the material given?	
	Are the conditions of teaching and learning carried out interactively and efficiently?	4
Turkey	Is the teaching and learning process done very well?	4.5
	Is the teaching and learning process carried out always on time?	4
	Does the knowledge provided to students meet all the learning curriculum needs?	5
	Is the assignment in accordance with the material given?	4
	Are the conditions of teaching and learning carried out interactively and efficiently?	4.5
Indonesia	Is the teaching and learning process done very well?	4.5
	Is the teaching and learning process carried out always on time?	4
	Does the knowledge provided to students meet all the learning curriculum needs?	4
	Is the assignment in accordance with the material given?	4
	Are the conditions of teaching and learning carried out interactively and efficiently?	4

On the other hand, although Turkey has a long education level (ES 4years - JHS 4years - SHS 4years) which is different from Japan and Indonesia. However, the results of observations show that the average value obtained from observations shows good values. Bearing in mind, Turkey is one of the developed countries in the European region which has complete information on the history of education. Various sciences from both Asia and Europe are found in large libraries located in Turkey[14].

The observations made at the Tebuireng Islamic Boarding School have a pretty good value when compared to Japan and Turkey. Given that Indonesia is a developing country that is improving the system towards the Revolutionary Era 4.0. However, the education system in Indonesia needs to be improved. Because the distribution of the education system in Indonesia is still lacking. Tebuireng Islamic Boarding School is one of the schools that represent

the Indonesian education system in general (not the best school, not the lowest school) in terms of the quality of education mirrors in Indonesia[15].The aim of education in Japan is "Education must aim at full development of personality and strive to preserve citizens, voice in mind and body, imbued with the qualities needed for those who form peaceful and democratic countries and societies."

The goals that are targeted to be achieved by Japanese education are:

1. Achievement of extensive knowledge and culture, cultivating a rich sensibility and sense of morality, and the development of a healthy body.
2. Developing individual abilities, fostering a spirit of autonomy and independence, and emphasizing the relationship between career and practical life.
3. Fostering an attitude of respecting justice and responsibility, mutual respect and cooperation, equality between men and women, and the civil spirit.
4. Fostering an attitude of respect for life and nature, and contributing to environmental protection.
5. Foster an attitude of respecting our traditions and culture, loving the countries and regions that nurture them, respecting other countries, and contributing to world peace and the development of the international community.

Although the number of Muslims in Japan is still relatively small, in building the personality of students, it is also emphasized to have a strong personality based on morals, enthusiasm, hard-working, disciplined and insight into Japanese nationality. These values and insights are evaluated through a number of learning activities inside and outside the classroom. Formally, junior high school subjects, 2-hour citizenship, 4-hour foreigners, 4-hour Japanese language, 4-hour mathematics, 4-hour science / science, 4-hour social studies, 2-hour arts and culture, 2-hour sports and health, information technology and 2 hour communication. As for high school subjects, citizenship 2 hours, Japanese 4 hours, foreign language 4 hours, mathematics 4 hours, physics 2 hours, chemistry 2 hours, biology 2 hours, geography 1 hour, history 1 hour, sociology 2 hours, art and culture 2 2 hours, sports and health, 2 hours information and communication technology and 2 hours self-service.

The aim of the education system in Turkey is to educate productive, happy individuals with a broad view on world affairs who will unite in national consciousness and think to form an inseparable state, and will contribute to the welfare of society through their skills. This is a thought that will play a role in shaping Turkey as a creative nation and

distinguishing its members from the modern world. Education in Turkey which is regulated by the National System which was established in accordance with attaturk reforms aims to produce skilled professional classes for the nation's social and economic institutions,

Turkish national education has several final goals, this has been established in the basic law of National Education Number 1739, namely:

1. To promote individuals who are committed and have principles, the concept of Nationalism as stipulated in the constitution, which adopts, protects and enhances the national, moral, human, spiritual and cultural values of the Turkish nation, who are aware of their duties and responsibilities towards the Republic of Turkey , a democratic, secular, and social state governed by law based on human rights and basic principles established at the beginning of the constitution.
2. To bring up individuals who are physically, mentally, morally, spiritually and emotionally possessing a moderate, healthy personality and mentality, independent and scientific thinking power, world-wide views, respecting human rights, respecting entrepreneurship and individuality, who fall under responsibility towards the community.
3. To prepare individuals for life by ensuring that they have a profession that will make them happy and contribute to the welfare of society through equipping them with the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes and work habits cooperatively in line with their own interests, talents and abilities.

Turkey, a country with a 99% Muslim population, has a very advanced international school. The education system in Turkey in general is almost the same as education in Indonesia. Secondary Education and Higher Education and non-school education. The high role of the community and companies (stakeholders) who care about the world of education, they set aside part of their income to build education[16].

The reason why they care so much about education is that their future countries will be led by their children now. Therefore, if they are given a good education, they will manage this country well later in time. Another reason they conveyed that in giving donations to schools they intended to do good deeds in accordance with religious teachings. In general we can see that education in Turkey really gets the attention of the government in addition to the awareness of citizens who have implications for the progress and prosperity of the country[17].The concept of education applied in pesantren has objectives that differ in detail from

Japan and Turkey. But in general, Islamic boarding schools have the same goal of teaching Ethics or Adab. Because the goals are guidelines for an institution in carrying out its functions. Preparation of Teaching Standardization in Islamic Boarding Schools is basically the purpose of establishing Islamic boarding schools divided into two things, namely:

1. General objectives, to foster citizens to have Muslim personalities in accordance with Islamic teachings and instill religious sense in all aspects of life as well as being useful to religion, society, nation and state.
2. Specific objectives, a) Educate students to become Muslim members of the community and to fear Allah SWT, have noble character, have intelligence, inner and outer skills as well as successful citizens. b) Educate students to become Muslim human beings as cadres of ulama, preachers, sincere, tough, tough, self-employed and practice sharia in full and dynamic way. c) Educating students to help remind the social welfare of the community in the context of efforts to develop society and the nation.

Islamic boarding school is a place to develop people to be good people as a school that was established also to educate students to be better and educate the nation's children. Pesantren has a teaching purpose that is designed very based on Islamic teachings with the aim of worship to get the blessing of Allah SWT, with a boarding system where kiai and santri live in the same place so that learning time is unlimited, and santri can be educated to become true believers who have integrity, who are strong, independent and have intellectual qualities[18].The environment of Japanese society that is currently known as a society that has the character of discipline, orderly, persistent, hard-working, law-abiding and polite. The character of this society is thought to be influenced by religious teachings that have developed since the past, especially in Buddhism and Shintoism. As narrated by Nakamura and Aiko, that Shinto religious education in the past has been targeted at schools in Japan. However, religious education, only lasted until World War II. After World War II ended, the Japanese government's policy was to abolish the religious education curriculum in Japanese government schools[19-21].

Unlike Turkey and Indonesia, Islam teaches manners in knowledge. Although Japan, has a difference with Turkey and Indonesia in terms of Religious Sciences, the results of the analysis in the success of the education system are based on the formation of good characters, such as tolerance, respect, polite in speaking, and polite in acting[22-25]. Attitudes like this, which reinforces the results that

successful education and success caused by the main factor that is etiquette. Although after education, real life and character formation are re-formed due to social conditions.

The learning model in these three countries illustrates that, inadvertent development of education is caused by the demands of technological development. Not only in Japan and Turkey, Islamic boarding schools also use technology such as computers, projectors, and also the internet as a medium for learning and information science. The use of e-books is due to the increasing development of information in digital form [26]. Make students need wifi internet facilities as a positive thing in the education environment [27, 28]. In this case, we conclude that the role of innovative learning models is inadvertently used in the education system in Japan, Turkey, and even Indonesia.

5. Discussions and Conclusion

The pesantren as an original Indonesian educational institution is an asset of the Indonesian nation that still survives to this day which is mainly based on the supply chain in education system. An institution can be said to be a pesantren if it has the following elements namely mosque, hut, santri, kiai and the teaching of the yellow book. One important thing is pesantren teaches the concept of simplicity and the concept of independence. Both of these concepts can be applied well in boarding schools because students learn and live away from family so that independence and simplicity is needed to survive in the concept of education in boarding schools. The advantage of pesantren is that learning can be done at any time directly because students and kyai (teachers) live in the same neighborhood. Although in social life, pesantren and schools in Japan and Turkey are different, the education system has the same general objective of prioritizing ethics and morals (adab) in the early stages of the education system at JHS or SHS levels. In addition, the achievement of educational service results in Islamic boarding schools is not too far from schools in Japan. Evidenced by an increase in students from Indonesia who managed to continue their tertiary education at higher education levels (Japan, Turkey, ect) and were able to compete with all students from various countries in the world by using supply chain strategies. Numerous schools have been enumerated by various authors in context of general education and Islamic education widely using area of various countries. Some authors have provided significant values of supply chain in the area of Islamic education which helps to build the characters and capabilities of students, while various authors have enumerated the general education standards with viable sources of success factors, while the study remained in conspiracy where the Islamic education has got much

attention rather than general education. The variant skills development has also been caught by various authors that mentioned the success factor of proper integration of educational system via supply chain.

In the era of industrial revolution, various approaches have been reviewed which provided significant results in the educational system integrations. The ability of anticipation has gained much importance in the era of Islamic education where the prioritization has been supported by the supply chain for ultimate success, while the ability to accommodate is also caught the success factor in establishing the system of education widely supply chain. The boarding schools has not only been caught significant in developing the self-organizing skills via such schools but also has provided some positivity in the character of such students in the memorizing the education better than in general schools.

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